

Introductions

Hello Dr.[name] , thank you for meeting with me.
I'm conducting research on mHealth apps in Indonesia.

We recently analysed thousands of user reviews and identified both **clear benefits** and a number of **common challenges** people face when using these apps.

I'd love to get your perspective as a GP, whether these findings resonate with your experience (or your patients'), and to hear any additional thoughts or experiences you might have.

The interview will take about 30 minutes. There are no right or wrong answers; feel free to share openly. Your input will help us understand what's really happening on the ground and how these apps might be improved for both providers and patients.

Questions

1. Have you personally used any digital health apps in your practice (for appointments, referrals, or patient management)?
 - a. If yes, which ones? If not, are you familiar with how these apps work for patients?
2. All (or some) of the apps happen to provide a broad range of services.
 - a. How do you find this one-stop service? Is it beneficial or is it too complex?
 - b. Have you heard about your patients' experience regarding this?
3. Users say these apps save them time, make healthcare more accessible, and allow them to consult or order medicines from home.
 - a. Do these benefits match what you've seen or heard in your practice?
 - b. Do you have any stories from your own experience or your patients that support or differ from these points?
4. Many users complain about difficult registration, repeated logins, and confusing or buggy profile forms.
 - a. Have your patients ever shared similar frustrations with you?
 - b. Have you noticed any particular groups (e.g., older patients) who struggle more with these steps?
 - c. What is the key information required for the sign-in process?
5. Some users report that app navigation is unclear, with unresponsive buttons or layouts that are hard to understand.
 - a. From your perspective, are the app interfaces easy for patients (or you) to use?
 - b. Are there common parts of the app where patients get "stuck" or make mistakes?
6. Frequent app crashes, slow loading, and constant forced updates are a major user complaint.
 - a. Have you or your patients experienced these technical problems?

- b. How does this impact the willingness to use the app, especially for urgent health needs?
- 7. Users often describe certain tasks (e.g., booking, getting refunds, or customer help) as too complicated, and support is seen as unresponsive or not helpful.
 - a. What has your or your patients' experience been with customer support or app-based help?
 - b. Do you think these processes could be simplified? How?
 - c. What kind of support your patients usually need and might need?
 - d. How should the support be delivered?
- 8. Some reviews mention that elderly, less tech-savvy people, or those with certain devices (or living abroad) have trouble using the apps.
 - a. Have you observed similar challenges?
 - b. Are there ways to make these apps more inclusive or user-friendly for everyone?
- 9. Are there other benefits or challenges you've seen that don't appear in these user reviews?
 - a. What would you most like to see improved or changed in mHealth apps for GPs or patients?
 - b. Any advice or insights for developers or policymakers?